

A Journal of Radix International Educational and
Research Consortium

RIJBFA

**RADIX INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
BANKING, FINANCE AND ACCOUNTING**

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF MUTUAL FUNDS: A REVIEW OF THE STUDIES FOR THE PAST DECADE

B. RAJA MANNAR

Department of Commerce
Sri Venkateswara University
Tirupati – 517502, India

ABSTRACT

The topic of the measurement of mutual funds performance is receiving an increasing interest both from an applied and a theoretical perspective. Beside the traditional financial literature, a growing body of studies has started to apply the tools of frontier analysis for benchmarking comparisons in portfolio analysis. The mutual fund industry has experienced huge growth internationally, becoming one of the primary vehicles through which individuals and most institutions invest in capital markets. Thus, the evaluation of the performance of mutual funds has become a very interesting research topic both for academic researchers for managers of financial, banking and investment institutions

An exhaustive survey of the literature pertaining to the performance evaluation, insight of investors on mutual funds for the past decade are presented. The review includes both Indian and foreign studies.

KEY WORDS : Performance evaluation, Mutual Funds, Bibliography over the past decade.

INTRODUCTION

Reviews of the studies relating to a field like mutual fund evaluation will help in identifying the thrust areas, shortcomings and suggestions for improvement.

Over the past few decades, mutual funds are playing a vital role in the economic development and this industry has flourished worldwide. In the light of these developments, the objective of this review is to identify the performance indicators of mutual funds and to analyse the impact of these performance indicators on mutual fund's performance. The study draws attention to the contradictions in the literature in the area of examining these performance indicators which have been identified as per the available literature as performance persistence, turnover, expense ratio, asset size, load fee, investment style, mutual fund managers and the ownership style of the mutual funds. A large number of studies on the growth and financial performance of mutual funds have been carried out during the past, in the developed and developing countries.

The review of literature is to funnel us in the methodologies to be used, estimation procedures and interpretation of results and therefore, focuses on both theoretical and empirical literature. The present paper presents a review of the studies on the performance of mutual funds over the past decade.

STUDIES IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

- **Dahlquist et al., (2000) (1)** in their study found negative relation between performance and fees. They show that high fee fund demonstrate lower performance, calculated using Jensen's alpha measure, compared to low fee funds. They found that in some cases high fee funds able to perform better than low fee fund before fees are deducted. They conclude that high fees – or expensive management – may generate good performance but not enough to cover the fees.
- **Indro et al (2001) (2)** report that an increase in net assets provides cost compensation because growth raises net returns. Brokerage commissions will decrease when trading in larger firms owing to larger transaction volume. Therefore, it is expected that valuable resources, including data, research services or supports and overhead costs can be shared. When fund sizes are increasing, a fund manager can focus more on strategies or investing in a more aggressive scenario. Therefore, ' total net assets ' is also one of the variables .
- **Thomas A Feuerborn (2001), (3)** argued that the individual investor will continue to be misled by mutual fund companies that market new funds. There no one is taking the completely honest approach that consumers can trust.
- **Boyson (2002) (4)** examined the relation between hedge fund manager characteristics and performance, volatility, and survival which provides a first look at the 'average' characteristics of a sample of hedge funds." She gathered information from 288 hedge funds from 1994-2000 and concluded that the relation between manager characteristics and volatility is more significant than manager characteristics and performance. Manager tenure had a negative relationship to returns and risk and the managers with longer tenure had worse non-volatility returns than those with shorter ones.

- **Edward S. O’Neal, Daniel E. Page, (2002) (5)** examined the sources of performance for a sample of mutual funds that invest primarily in utility companies. Given recent deregulation developments in the utility industry and the sub-market performance of utility stocks in the 1990s, hypothesized that utility funds may be considering alternatives to traditional high-yielding electric utility stocks. Although there is anecdotal evidence that utility funds may be tilting their focus away from electric utility stocks, utility mutual funds as a group are no more or less heavily invested in utility stocks today than they have been over the past 10 years.
- **Fortin *et al* (2002) (6)** found that manager tenure and turnover have a negative relationship. However, manager tenure and mutual funds size are positively related. Therefore, investors are advised to consider factors (other than manager tenure) in light of other investment elements, which might affect performance – namely, turnover, fund size and expense ratio.
- **Syriopoulos (2002) (7)** gave a review on an analysis of investor’s risk perception towards mutual funds services. Financial markets are constantly becoming more efficient by providing more promising solutions to the investors. Being a part of financial markets although mutual funds industry is responding very fast by analyze investor’s perception and expectations.
- **Berk and Green (2004) (8)** argue that mutual fund market equilibrium is attained through fund flows. These respond to past performance, but due to decreasing returns to scale in active fund management, the growth in fund size of recent winner funds causes their performance to deteriorate, while loser-fund performance benefits from withdrawals that force managers to reoptimize their portfolios.
- **Mary Jane Lenard et al. (9)** empirically investigates investor attitudes toward mutual funds. The model, based on investor responses, develops an investor's "risk profile" variable. Results indicate that regardless of whether the investors invest in nonemployer plans or in both employer and nonemployer plans, they consider their investment risk,

fund performance, investment mix, and the capital base of the fund before switching funds. The model developed in this study can also assist in predicting investors' switching behavior.

- **Qiu (2003) (10)** suggest that employment risk concerns could lead to fund managers taking less risk. Besides these agency incentives, there are other risk considerations, such as unskilled managers making poor investment decisions and skilled managers taking advantage of market timing opportunities. Further, behavioral factors may also affect risk shifting behavior. Prospect theory) suggests that successful fund managers might suddenly become risk averse. In contrast, overconfidence has been recognized as influencing the behavior of both retail investors and institutional investors.
- **Ronald T. Wilcox (2003), (11)** examined how investors choose a mutual fund and found that investors pay a great attention to past performance and also indicated that the educated investors demonstrated greater knowledge of basic finance made poorer, not better, decisions than their less financially savvy.
- **Susan Coleman(2003),(12)** examined and compared the attitude towards risk and holding of risky assets of black, white and Hispanic households using data from the 1998 survey of Consumer Finances. The result shows that Hispanic heads of household were more risk averse and they are unwilling to take any risk in exchange for investment returns. Black and white households are not more risk averse even though there is different asset mix. The study has also found that women and older heads of household express a higher degree of risk aversion and hold a lower percentage of risky assets. Similarly, it found that more highly educated individuals and wealthier heads of households express a lower degree of risk aversion and hold a higher percentage of risky assets.
- **Berk and Green (2004) (13)** argue that mutual fund market equilibrium is attained through fund flows. These respond to past performance, but due to decreasing returns to scale in active fund management, the growth in fund size of recent winner funds

causes their performance to deteriorate, while loser-fund performance benefits from withdrawals that force managers to reoptimize their portfolios

- **Dimitrios F. Kenourgios And Ioannis Petropoulos (2004) (14)** examined the past performances of mutual funds as a criterion for investors' future choices. In particular, examined if mutual funds Persistence was tested by constructing two-way tables showing the successful performance over successive two-year and one year period. Afterwards, simulated a strategy of investing in the top performing mutual funds during the preceding two years and concluded that in 1990s persistence is weak, Strong evidence was not found that past returns provide information about future returns. As most of the results in relevant studies, results may be subject to survivorship bias.
- **Paula A. Tkac (2004), (15)** found that investors are irrational or in some other sense cannot look out for their own best interests. Consumer who prefer more style, features or power willingly pay higher prices and the investor rely on and pay to the financial advisors or brokers for processing and formulating guidance regarding fund allocation. They are facing risk because of misconduct by advisory firms. They are not demanding any disclosures of their fund. The risks reduced to zero if investors are willing to pay with their own time and energy to monitor their fund position.
- **Spiegel (2004) (16)** indicated that the security returns follow linear factor model with constant coefficients. This paper develops and estimates a Kalman filter statistical model to track time-varying fund alphas and betas. Several tests indicate that relative to a rolling OLS model the Kalman filter model produces more accurate fund factor loadings both in and out of sample.
- **Zhao (2004) (17)** reviewed fund families typically and claim that closing a fund protects the fund superior performance by preventing it from growing too large to be managed efficiently. Even though funds with better performance and larger size are more likely to be closed, there is no evidence that closing a fund can indeed protect its performance. Instead, fund closing decisions are more likely to be motivated by spillover effects – by

closing a star fund, the fund family signals its superior performance and also bring investors attention and investments to other funds in the family. Some evidence exists to suggest that the closing strategy is effective in generating higher inflows into the rest of the family, at least in the short run.

- **Athanasious G. et al., (2005), (18)** evaluated the performance of 23 equity funds during the period 1997-2000 in Greece. The performance evaluation was based on measuring risk and return of the selected funds and the study proves that the investor needs to know the long term behavior of Mutual funds in order to make the right investment decision.
- **Cinzia Daraio and Le´opold Simar (2005) (19)** contributed to the literature proposing a robust nonparametric approach for analysing mutual funds. It is based on the concept of order-m frontier. Introducing environmental variables in nonparametric frontier models: to find out the factors explaining mutual funds performance. Within this framework, a decomposition of conditional efficiency is proposed, and its usefulness for economic interpretation analysed. Economies of scale, slacks and market risks are investigated. A comparison of traditional, nonparametric and robust performance measures is also offered.
- **Gullett and Redman (2005) (20)** maintain that a negative relationship exists between expense ratio, and higher expenses will reduce risk-adjusted returns; hence, more cost efficient funds should generate higher returns when all other elements are held constant. Furthermore, Khorana (loc. Cit.) maintains that the overall effect of reducing total fund expenses leads to a higher level of price sensitivity with a greater of economic scales of investors.
- **Shefrin and Singal and Xu, (2011). (21)** documents that past outperformance triggers large inflows, but that investors in poorly performing funds fail to withdraw their investments. Explanations for such behavior include the anticipation of either a strategy change by the incumbent manager, or the firing of a poorly performing manager, or a

disposition effect. Consequently, the persistence of poor performance might be due to investor inertia.

- **Zakri Y.Bello (2005) (22)** matched a sample of socially responsible stock mutual funds matched to randomly selected conventional funds of similar net assets to investigate differences in characteristics of assets held, degree of portfolio diversification and variable effects of diversification on investment performance.
 - **Costa, Jakob, and Porter (2006) (23)** varied their research from the others previously mentioned by examining how market trends and manager experience impact the ability of managers to generate positive risk-adjusted returns. They set out to find whether risk-adjusted returns from 1990-2001 were due to manager experience or market conditions. The conclusion : managers in a bull market underperformed the market and during a bear market outperformed it.
 - **Gallagher, Nadarajay, and Pinnuck (2006) (24)** find that after replacement, poorly performing funds improve performance, but not because of better stock selection. Performance is enhanced primarily through decreased momentum investment strategies and decreased portfolio concentration. If performance is affected by the replacement of the fund manager, then the timing of the replacement may also be important. The timing of mutual fund manager replacement has not been previously examined.
 - **Gottesman and Morey (2006) (25)** examined the relation between manager education and mutual fund performance. They used a data set of 518 mutual funds from 2000-2003 in a non-bullish market to contrast Chevalier and Ellison. The latter had been criticized for examining managers during a bull market from 1988-1994 where the younger managers succeeded because they took on more risk generally than the veterans and thus reaped a greater reward.
 - **Jonathan B. Berk and Ian Tonks (2006) (26)** document that the observed persistence amongst the worst performing actively managed mutual funds is attributable to funds
-

that have performed poorly both in the current and prior year and demonstrated that this persistence results from an unwillingness of investors in these funds to respond to bad performance by withdrawing their capital. In contrast, funds that only performed poorly in the current year have a significantly larger outflow of funds/return sensitivity and show no evidence of persistence in their returns.

- **Keswani and Stolin (2006) (27)** grouped UK mutual funds data from the years 1991-2001 into four categories: domestic equity, domestic non-equity, global equity and global non-equity. They then studied if performance persistence is dependent on the level of competition within the group, defining high competition as low concentration of assets under management. The authors found significant persistence for all categories and concluded that persistence was positively related to concentration.
- **Bergstresser (2007) (28)** stipulates that many investors purchase mutual funds through intermediated channels, paying brokers for fund selection and advice. Brokers sold funds exhibit no more skill at aggregate-level asset allocation than do funds sold through the direct channel. The results are consistent either with substantial non-tangible benefits delivered by the broker distributed sector or with conflicts of interest between brokers and their clients.
- **Elton, Gruber, and Green (2007) (29)** are of the opinion that mutual fund returns are more closely correlated within families than across families.
- **Franco and Zhou (2007) (30)** examined whether equity analysts with CFA designation outperformed those who had none. Two important contributing factors that played a major role in their results were timeliness and boldness of the managers. Using a sample of 4,380 analysts from 1999-2003, they found that CFA charter holders issued moderately timelier and bolder forecasts. Furthermore, with timeliness controlled, CFA managers tended to be more accurate than non-CFA's. Their tests also indicated that managers with a CFA performed at a higher level than those without one.

- **Jiang (2007) (31)** uses the holding-based tests and find that actively monitored U.S. domestic equity mutual funds have positive timing ability; fund managers can time the market in response not only to macroeconomic conditions, but also to private information.
- **Switzer and Huang (2007) (32)** picked up where Shukla and Singh left off by examining whether small and mid cap mutual funds were affected by manager characteristics of tenure, investment experience, MBA, CFA, age, and gender. Switzer and Huang gathered a sample of 1,004 small and mid cap equity funds to conduct their research. Of the desired manager characteristics, the only one that had a positive effect on fund performance measured by excess returns or alpha was the CFA designation.
- The studies by **Timotej Jagrica, Boris Podobnikb, Sebastjan Straseka, Vita Jagrica (2007) (33)** on the mutual fund industry applies various tests to evaluate the performance capacity of mutual funds which included the data, and then introduces the performance measures used to evaluate funds. Finally, the performance measures of mutual funds was calculated and ranked them according to the results. The rankings obtained by performing both the Sharpe and Treynor rules to be almost the same, implying that funds are well diversified. The rankings reveal that all analyzed funds outperformed the market on a risk-adjusted basis.
- Recent research has focused on many of the characteristics separately, attempting to quantify the effect each has on fund returns. Even more recently, studies such as **Bliss et al (2008) (34)** have attempted to combine many of these effects in order to analyze the combined impact of such factors. This study looks to combine these factors in order to examine a new scenario, connecting fund fees, fund style, and fund performance in relation to individual and team management. The results of this study will attempt to demonstrate where an investor will be better off investing their money in regards to management structure and fees.

- **Dangl, Wu and Zechner (2008) (35)** developed a theoretical model of the mutual fund industry in which poorly performing managers are subject to both external governance through market discipline with investors withdrawing funds, and internal governance in the form of manager replacement. The new manager also tends to change the fund's risk profile relative to her predecessor. For most parameter values in the calibrated model, there will be capital outflows and a portfolio risk increase before replacement, as the fund manager anticipating a termination of the employment contract takes on more risk in the hope of getting lucky.. After the manager is replaced, the model predicts that there will be capital inflows and a decrease in portfolio risk.
 - **Haslem et al (2008) (36)** point out that management fees account for the largest parts of expense ratios and reveal a positive effect on the expense ratio. Furthermore, investors are likely to purchase higher performing mutual funds; for example, the mutual fund companies can use the extra money to cover fixed costs, which, in turn, should assist in reducing the expense ratios. Therefore, when funds sizes are increasing, the managements become more efficient in operating from economies of scales by reducing the expense ratios. 6 Thus, fund asset size and performance have a positive relationship.
 - Based on the findings of **Pollet and Wilson (2008) (37)** that fund managers scale up existing holdings as a response to inflows, it could be the case that fund flows and manager changes are complements among winner funds. Specifically, if managerial skill determines the number of "best ideas" a manager is able to generate and the newly hired manager has lower skills relative to the former manager, then the same level of inflows should have a stronger impact on the performance of winner funds with a manager change than on those without a change of manager.
 - **Ruenzi and Kempf (2008) (38)**, in an Empirical Study of "Indian Individual Investors' Behaviour" attempted to know the profile of the investors and also to know their characteristics so as to know their preference with respect to their investments. The
-

study also tried to unravel the influence of demographic factors like gender and age on risk tolerance level of the investors.

- **Wu, Chang and Wu (2008) (39)** try to find how investors evaluate mutual fund performance, not only based on quantitative but also on qualitative criteria. They conclude that the most important criteria of mutual fund performance should be mutual fund style following with market investment environment. Investors should concentrate more on gathering information of mutual fund style when selecting investment vehicles. They recommend that mutual fund issuers should try to provide more information related to mutual fund style and the investment environment.
 - **Comer, Larrymore and Rodriguez (2009) (40)** find that hybrid funds perform significantly better than the style benchmarks under weak stock market conditions. They define hybrid as both asset allocation and balanced mutual funds that hold a combination of equities, fixed income securities and cash in their portfolios. These funds engage in both security selection and market timing.
 - **Ivković and Weisbenner (2009) (41)** studied on Individual investor mutual fund flows. They studied the relation between individuals mutual fund flows and funds characteristics, establishing three key results. First, consistent with tax motivations, individual investors are reluctant to sell mutual funds that have appreciated in value and are willing to sell losing funds. Second, individuals pay attention to investment costs as redemption decisions are sensitive to both expense ratios and loads.
 - **James L. Kuhle and Rafiqul Bhuyan, (2009) (42)** examined whether mutual fund managers who have concentrated in real estate assets have statistically outperformed other categories of equity mutual funds as well as the S&P 500 and various NAREIT Indexes.
 - **Kempf, Ruenzi and Thiele, (2009) (43)** suggest that employment risk concerns could lead to fund managers taking less risk, Besides these agency incentives, there are other risk considerations, such as unskilled managers making poor investment decisions and
-

skilled managers taking advantage of market timing opportunities. Further, behavioral factors may also affect risk shifting behavior. Prospect theory) suggests that successful fund managers might suddenly become risk averse. In contrast, overconfidence has been recognized as influencing the behavior of both retail investors and institutional investors Overconfidence can be explained by biased self-attribution, whereby individuals update their beliefs about their own ability as being attributable to skill following good outcomes, but due to bad luck after bad outcomes. They become more overconfident after good past performance, but not less confident after bad past performance There exist several reasons to believe that fund flows and manager changes.

- The research paper of **Nur Atiqah Abdullah and Nur Adiana Hiau Abdullah (2009) (44)** investigates the relationship between unit trusts invested domestically and those invested overseas. The performance of unit trusts investing overseas is compared to unit trusts that are invested locally to determine whether they outperform the local funds. The Kuala Lumpur Composite Index (KLCI) is used as the local funds' benchmark. The Morgan Stanley Capital international All Country (MSCI AC) Asia Pacific and MSCI World Free are utilised as the international funds' benchmarks. With a total of 26 local funds and 23 internationally invested funds, it is found that the risk-adjusted performance of internationally diversified funds is not significantly different from the performance of well-diversified domestic funds.
- **Choi, Laibson, and Madrian (2008) (45)** suggest that clients will likely be grateful for the efforts to minimize expenses in order to increase expected risk-adjusted return. This effort to minimize expenses can also be highlighted when meeting with new clients in order to ease potential concerns about the additional cost of the financial planner.
- **Hereil, Pierre, Mitaine, Philippe, Moussavi, Nicolas and Roncalli, Thierry (2010) (46)** studies the persistence of mutual fund performance. Academic research often focuses on fund returns, sometimes adjusted for style and market cap biases. Because fund rating systems play a central role in the asset management industry, another approach

was considered. Using a Markov modeling of these ratings, illustrated that the persistence of the performance is relatively poor with respect to the time horizon of investors. It was shown that two facts may explain these results. First, the rating system is not necessarily time-homogeneous. Second, the importance of style is crucial when comparing the ratings of mutual funds. However, it was observed that it is extremely difficult to characterize quantitatively the style of a mutual fund.

- **Cici (2011) (47)** finds, after controlling for property type, size and momentum factors, that REIT mutual funds possess significant selection abilities.
- The study by **Hui-chuan Chen (2011) (48)** examines 60 mutual funds and data for the same group of mutual funds were obtained as of 30 September 2008 to evaluate the recommendations provided in Consumer Reports. In order to exclude the major declines that occurred in the stock market in October 2008, the time periods of 30 November 2006 and 30 September 2008 were analyzed in this study. Specifically, this research examines the relationship between mutual funds' net assets, share prices, manager tenures, expense ratio, tax – cost ratio and annualized returns to see whether Consumer Reports is a reliable source for investors seeking to purchase mutual funds.
- In their study, **Irfan Ullah Shah et al. (2012) (49)** have evaluated the performance of conventional and Islamic mutual funds in Pakistan. The data set consisted of 125 funds in which 94 was conventional and 31 Islamic mutual funds. The results indicated that Islamic mutual fund performed better with Sharpe ratio -3.045 which is better than conventional mutual funds (-3.7152). Both funds have underperformed from their benchmark, Islamic mutual funds were well diversified ($R^2=0.99$) while conventional mutual fund had low diversification rate ($R^2=.48$). The overall performance of Islamic mutual fund having less risk rate 1.03% and giving average return higher than the market average return while the conventional mutual fund risk rate is 4.41% but the average rate of return is below the market return.

- **Jin-Li Hu, (2012) (50)** applies a four-stage data envelopment analysis (DEA) approach to measure the operational environment-adjusted efficiency of sixty mutual funds in Taiwan from 2006 to 2010 which adopted the approach for adjusting negative output. In addition, the truncated regression model is used to estimate effects of environmental variables on input slacks in the second stage. The efficiency of funds initially lightly declined, rapidly rose during the financial crisis of 2008, and then gradually fell again. Manager attributes as well as fund characteristics significantly affect the performance of mutual funds. This research finds that the Balance fund performs better than the others and female managers perform more outstandingly than male managers both in cost control and risk management.
- **Konstantina Pendaraki (2012) (51)** presented Data Envelopment Analysis, a nonparametric approach, for the evaluation of mutual fund performance of both mean-variance and higher moment's framework on data of Greek mutual funds over the period 2007-2010 with encouraging results.
- The research of **Majid Abbasi and Majid Dadashinasab (2012) (52)** examined the effects of mutual fund managers' characteristics on the performance of Iranian mutual funds. The research was carried out on all Iranian mutual funds during 2007 to 2011. Generalized Lease Square (GLS) was employed to examine these effects. The results show that fund manager's Age, MBA, Gender, and Tenure significantly influence fund performance.
- The study by **Nasir Razzaq (2012) (53)** observed that returns of funds are according to their level of risk. We have also investigated the performance and ability of funds managers by the help of different models, such as sharp ratio, Trenyor ratio, Jensen's Alpha and information ratio.

STUDIES IN INDIA

- The following is a brief account of articles published in books, financial dailies, magazines and research journals by academicians, professionals and journalists, explaining the concepts of mutual funds, its importance, features, schemes, investment pattern, method of reading a mutual fund prospectus, guidelines to choose a scheme and significance of IMFI.
- **Irissappane Aravazhi (2000) (54)** evaluated the investment pattern and performance of 34 close-end schemes from 1988-98 and elicited the views of investors and managers belonging to Chennai, Mumbai, Pune and Delhi. The survey identified that the investors desired a return equivalent to market. 16 schemes reported greater risk than the market volatility. Majority of the schemes had a lower beta. Negative values in the case of Treynor and Sharpe index among many schemes indicated the mockery of the market and identified that the fund managers of 26 schemes had missed the chance.
- **Jain (2000) (55)** provided an analysis considering whether funds advertising following a period of superior performance exhibit continued superior performance. They use a sample of 294 funds that are advertised in either Barron's or Money magazine. They consider returns in the year both pre and post advertisement, finding the post advertisement period performance of the funds is, on average, significantly inferior when compared to their benchmarks. This leads them to conclude that pre advertisement superior performance is not due to skill and that out-performance of advertised funds.
- **Roshni Jayam's (2002)(56)** study brought out that equities had a good chance of appreciation in future. The researcher was of the view that, investors should correctly judge their investment objective and risk appetite before picking schemes, diversified equity funds were typically safer than others and index funds were the best when

market movements were not certain and suggested Systematic Withdrawal Plan (SWP) with growth option was more suitable for investors in need of regular cash inflows.

- Research article by **Rajeeva Sinha and Vijay Jog(2005) (57)** provides evidence on the magnitude of the difference between returns to mutual fund investors (IRR, hereafter) and the returns reported by mutual funds (RR, hereafter). The finding that mutual fund investors chase above average performing funds , are reluctant to book losses and the evidence on declining performance persistence amongst mutual funds raises the possibility that IRR may be lower than RR. This study provides the first ever evidence on the magnitude of the difference between IRR and RR for mutual fund investors.
- **Anand and Murugaiah (2006) (58)** examined the components and sources of investment performance in order to attribute it to specific activities of Indian fund managers. They also attempted to identify a part of observed return which is due to the ability to pick up the best securities at given level of risk. For this purpose, Fama's methodology is adopted. The study covers the period between April 1999 and March 2003 and evaluates the performance of mutual funds based on 113 selected schemes having exposure more than 90% of corpus to equity stocks of 25 fund houses. The empirical results reported reveal the fact that the mutual funds were not able to compensate the investors for the additional risk that they have taken by investing in the mutual funds. The study concludes that the influence of market factor was more severe during negative performance of the funds while the impact selectivity skills of fund managers was more than the other factors on the fund performance in times of generating positive return by the funds. It can also be observed from the study that selectivity, expected market risk and market return factors have shown closer correlation with the fund return.
- **Nalini Prava Tripathy (2006) (59)** evaluated the market timing abilities of Indian fund managers of thirty-one tax planning schemes in India over the period Dec. 1995 to January, 2004 by using Jensen & Mazuy Model and Henriksson and Merton model. The

study indicates that the fund managers have not been successful in reaping returns in excess of the market, and timing the market in the wrong direction.

- **Rao D. N (2006) (60)** studied the financial performance of select open-ended equity mutual fund schemes for the period 1st April 2005 - 31st March 2006 pertaining to the two dominant investment styles and tested the hypothesis whether the differences in performance are statistically significant. The analysis indicated that growth plans have generated higher returns than that of dividend plans but at a higher risk studied and classified the 419 open-ended equity mutual fund schemes into six distinct investment styles.
 - **Rao and Schaub (2006) (61)** recognized that in 89 per cent of the cases, funds with lower expense ratios than their counterparts outperform those with higher expense ratios. Lower expense ratios cannot guarantee better performance; however, when investors choose funds with low expense ratios, they generally have a better chance of receiving greater overall returns.
 - **Hanumantha Rao, P and Vijay K.R. Mishra (2007) (62)** in their article “Mutual Fund: A Resource Mobiliser in Financial Market” made a critical study of the role performed by Mutual Funds as a financial service in Indian Financial Market.
 - **Sanjay Kant Khare (2007) (63)** opined that investors could purchase stocks or bonds with much lower trading costs through mutual funds and enjoy the advantages of diversification and lower risk. The researcher identified that, with a higher savings rate of 23 percent, channeling savings into mutual funds sector has been growing rapidly as retail investors were gradually keeping out of the primary and secondary market. Mutual funds have to penetrate into rural areas with diversified products, better corporate governance and through introduction of financial planners.
 - **Guha (2008) (64)** focused on return-based style analysis of equity mutual funds in India using quadratic optimization of an asset class factor model proposed by William Sharpe. The study found the “Style Benchmarks” of each of its sample of equity funds as
-

optimum exposure to 11 passive asset class indexes. The study also analyzed the relative performance of the funds with respect to their style benchmarks. The results of the study showed that the funds have not been able to beat their style benchmarks on the average.

- **Agrawal Deepak & Patidar Deepak (2009) (65)** studied the empirically testing on the basis of fund manager performance and analyzing data at the fund-manager and fund-investor levels. The study revealed that the performance is affected by the saving and investment habits of the people and at the second side the confidence and loyalty of the fund Manager and rewards- affects the performance of the MF industry in India.
- **Kavitha (2009) (66)** documented that the ignorance of the investors about mutual funds coupled with aggressive selling by promising higher returns of the investors have resulted in loss of investors' confidence due to inability to provide higher return. The agents or distributors of mutual funds are more governed by the incentives they get for selling the schemes and not by the requirements of the investors and quality of the products and do not explain the risk factors to the investors.
- **Ravi Kiran(2009), (67)** highlighted that volatility influencing stock market movements. The article revealed that mutual funds are most preferred financial avenue but needs some innovation and added quality dimensions in existing services.
- **Sathya Swaroop Debasish, (2009) (68)** attempted to study the performance of selected schemes of mutual funds based on risk-return relationship models and measures. A total of 23 schemes offered by six private sector mutual funds and three public sector mutual funds have been studied over the time period April 1996 to March 2009 (13 years). The analysis has been made on the basis of mean return, beta risk, coefficient of determination, Sharpe ratio, Treynor ratio and Jensen Alpha. The overall analysis finds Franklin Templeton and UTI being the best performers and Birla SunLife, HDFC and LIC mutual funds showing poor below-average performance when measured against the risk-return relationship models.

- **Prabakaran and Jayabal (2010) (69)** evaluated the performance of a sample of 23 schemes , chosen as per the priority given by the respondents in Dharmapuri district covered a period from April 2002 to March 2007. The study used the methodology of Sharpe, Jensen and Fama for the performance evaluation of mutual funds. The results of the study found that 13 schemes out of 23 schemes selected had superior performance than the benchmark portfolio in terms of Sharpe ratio, 13 schemes had superior performance of Treynor ratio and 14 schemes had superior performance according to Jensen measure. The Fama's measure indicated in the study that the returns out of diversification were less.
- **Ranganathan, Kavitha (2006) (70)** made an attempt to examine the related aspects of the fund selection behaviour of individual investors towards Mutual funds, in the city of Mumbai.
- **Sondhi and Jain (2010) (71)** examined the market risk and investment performance of equity mutual funds in India. The study used a sample of 36 equity fund for a period of 3 years. The study examined whether high beta of funds have actually produced high returns over the study period. The study also examined that open-ended or close ended categories, size of fund and the ownership pattern significantly affect risk-adjusted investment performance of equity fund. The results of the study confirmed with the empirical evidence produced by Fama that high beta funds (market risks) may not necessarily produced high returns. The study revealed that the category, size and ownership have been significantly determinant of the performance of mutual funds during the study period.
- **Devasenathipathi (2011) (72)** investigated the performance of public-sector and private-sector mutual funds for the period of 2005 to 2007. Selected funds of LIC (Public sector) and Reliance (Private sector) were chosen for the purpose of analysis.. The study revealed that performance of all the funds seemed to be volatile during the study period; as such it was quite difficult to earmark one particular fund that out performed

consistently and proposed a model that focuses performance of actively managed equity mutual funds and found that a fund manager can generate state-dependent active returns at a disutility. Negative expected performance and mutual fund investing simultaneously arise in equilibrium.

- **Garg (2011) (73)** examined the performance of top ten mutual funds that was selected on the basis of previous years return. The study analyzed the performance on the basis of return, standard deviation, beta as well as Treynor, Jensen and Sharpe indexes. The study also used Carhart's four-factor model for analyze the performance of mutual funds. The results revealed that Reliance Regular Saving Scheme Fund had achieved the highest final score and Canara Robeco Infra had achieved the lowest final score in the one year category.
- **Manisha Goel and Shelly Singhal (2011) (74)** aimed at evaluating the performance of SIP plans against one time investment. HDFC mutual funds return has been compared with the HDFC SIP return for the past 10 year period from April1, 2001 to Feb, 28,2011.For this purpose we have used annual returns based on NAV.CRISIL has been used as a proxy for benchmark return, while annual yields on 364-day Treasury bill as a surrogate for the Risk free rate of Return.. The Empirical result reported that SIP Plans has performed better than the one time investment. The various SIP Plans available, top five plans have been found out by ranking of the Returns from the various kinds of SIP Plans.
- The study of **Santhi and Gurunatham (2012) (75)** finds that the participation of investors in Tax saving mutual funds is comparatively less than other safer investment areas like Insurance, Postal Deposit Schemes and Fixed Deposits. The dynamic relationship between investors' biographical information and their behavior has been examined by using relevant statistical techniques. The investors' Knowledge and satisfaction on Tax saving mutual funds and awareness on regulating bodies also has been analyzed. The study finds that majority of the investor doesn't have the

knowledge on schemes and awareness on controlling authorities and they are satisfied with the overall benefits on Tax saving mutual funds.

- **Selvam et.al (2011) (76)** studied the risk and return relationship of Indian mutual fund schemes. The study found out that out of thirty five sample schemes, eleven showed significant t-values and all other twenty four sample schemes did not prove significant relationship between the risk and return. According to t-alpha values, majority (32) of the sample schemes' returns were not significantly different from their market returns and very few number of sample schemes' returns were significantly different from their market returns during the study period.
 - The study by **Simran Saini et al. (2011) (77)** presented analyses the mutual fund investments in relation to investor's behavior. Investors' opinion and perception has been studied relating to various issues like type of mutual fund scheme, main objective behind investing in mutual fund scheme, role of financial advisors and brokers, investors' opinion relating to factors that attract them to invest in mutual funds, sources of information, deficiencies in the services provided by the mutual fund managers, challenges before the Indian mutual fund industry.
 - Using various statistical measures the a study aiming to evaluate the performance of a few selected income or debt mutual funds schemes of India on the basis of their daily NAV recorded in the period starting on 1st April 2000 upto 31st March 2010 was reported by **Sumninder Kaur Bawa and Smiti Brar. (2011) (80)** The work also compares the results of public sector sponsored schemes with that of private sector schemes. Popularity of income schemes has only increased in the last decade. Income mutual funds they have seen tremendous growth in their number of schemes from 91 on 31st march 2001 to 330 on 31st march 2010. 506 in 2008 was the maximum ever in terms of total schemes floating in the market. This category has seen a decline only twice in the last decade. First fall was posted in the year 2003 and the second fall was reported in the year 2010. One striking fact which comes to light is the huge percentage
-

contribution of income schemes towards the total AUM of the Indian mutual funds industry. On the basis of the facts and figures it can be easily concluded that looking at the parameter of average annual NAV and its percentage growth rate, private sector leads the race. As per the data collected it was stated that private sector mutual fund ICICI Prudential Income Fund (growth option) gave the maximum return as compared to other schemes considered in the study. Another conclusion which can be derived keeping in view the standard deviation is that public sector income schemes are more unpredictable when it comes to assessing returns.

- The research article by **Surinder Kr. Miglani (2011) (81)** analyzes Indian mutual fund managers' market timing ability for the period of 1999-2004 using Jensen & Mazuy Module and Henriksson & Merton Module. To achieve the goal a sample of ninety eight mutual fund schemes having different investment objectives, both from public as well as private sector, have been selected. The study finds that Indian mutual fund managers are unable to test the market timing of the mutual fund schemes and relying only on stock selection skill for getting maximum return. It implies that they are generating superior performance due to largely involvement in security selection.
- **Avani Shah and Narayan Baser (2012) (82)** studied the investor's preference in selection of Mutual fund and measuring the fund sponsor quality. In this paper, research of 305 mutual fund investors was conducted in Ahmedabad using non-probability convenience sampling. After using One-Way ANNOVA, researcher had come to a conclusion that Funds reputation, Withdrawal facilities, brand name, Sponsor's past performance in terms of risk & return varies among the investor's of different age group & investor's different occupation group.
- An attempt was to study the performance evaluation of selected open ended schemes in terms of risk and return relationship by **Bimal Anjum. (2012) (83)**. For this rate of return method, Beta, Standard Deviation, Sharpe ratio and Treynor ratio has been used. BSE-30 has been used as a benchmark to study the performance of mutual funds

in India. The study period was from 1st April 2009 to 31st March 2011. The findings of the study reveal that only three schemes have performed better than benchmark.

- **Bijan Roy and Kaushik Bhattacharjee (2012) (84)** calculates the Performance Change measure (PCM) developed by Grinblatt & Titman (Journal of Business, 1993, vol 66, no-1, loc.cit.) for a sample of 50 Indian mutual funds over a period of 26 months. PCM as a measure has some advantages compared to the traditional measures, the most important one being –it is free from using a benchmark portfolio and consequently the resulting biases arising out of usage of such a portfolio. So by using PCM as a measure, this paper, without using any benchmark, attempts to assess whether the selected mutual funds are able to provide above-normal return on average –using no more information than what is available to the common investor. PCM has been calculated for one month, one quarter and one year lag. And using PCM as a measure the study finds that though in the short term, the mutual funds were unable to generate above-normal return but on the average the combined PCM of all the mutual funds is significantly different from zero.
- **Ghose, Soheli (2012) (85)** has studied the effect and role of Sector Holdings on the Performance of Mutual Funds in the fluctuating financial markets analysing 1 public sector (UTI Opportunities) and 2 private sector mutual fund schemes (HDFC Equity, Tata Equity PE) between January 2010 and September 2011 covering the turbulent period of this economic crisis.
- The main objective of the study of **Gomathy Thyagarajan (2012) (86)** is to evaluate the performance of the sample schemes of Franklin Templeton, HDFC and ICICI Prudential mutual funds and to measure the risk/volatility in order to arrive at the appropriate risk-adjusted rate of return using W.F. Sharpe's method. An attempt is made by the researcher to evaluate the performance of the sample schemes by using the Sharpe ratio which measures the excess return per unit of total risk.

- **Kalpesh P Prajapati, and Mahesh K Patel (87)** outlined the performance evaluation of Indian mutual funds is carried out through relative performance index, risk-return analysis, Treynor's ratio, Sharp's ratio, Sharp's measure, Jensen's measure, and Fama's measure. The study period is 1st January 2007 to 31 December, 2011. The results of performance measures suggest that most of the mutual fund have given positive return during 2007 to 2011.
- **Nimalathasan and Kumar Gandhi (2012) (88)** focused on the financial performance analysis of mutual fund schemes (equity diversified schemes and equity mid-cap schemes) of selected banks (State Bank of India, Canara Bank- Public Bank, ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank-Private Bank).The objectives of this research work is to analysis the financial performance of selected mutual fund schemes through the statistical parameters and ratio analysis. Among the Open ended – Tax Saving schemes, Canara Robeco Equity Diversified is the preferred and ranked top most, at the same time among the Open ended – Midcap schemes, HDFC Capital Builder is the preferred and ranked top through various tools.
- **Ravi Vyas, (2012) (89)** focused attention on number of factors that highlights investors' perception about mutual funds. It was found that mutual funds were not that much known to investors, still investor rely upon bank and post office deposits, most of the investor used to invest in mutual fund for not more than 3 years and they used to quit from the fund which were not giving desired results. Equity option and SIP mode of investment were on top priority in investors' list. It was also found that maximum number of investors did not analyse risk in their investment and they depend upon their broker and agent.
- **Sahit Chowdary Garapati (2012) (90)** attempted to provide a benchmark or guide to investors to select the cream layer of equity mutual funds. So, in this pursuit, we have categorized mutual funds into Large Cap, Mid Cap and Sectoral based on their AUM and

sector specificity and ranked them based on their risk adjusted return values using a new index based approach.

- **Sarita Bahl and Meenakshi Rani (2012) (91)** investigated the performance of 29 open-ended, growth-oriented equity schemes for the period from April 2005 to March 2011, of transition economy.. BSE-sensex has been used for market portfolio. The historical performance of the selected schemes were evaluated on the basis of Sharpe, Treynor, and Jensen's measure, The study revealed that 14 out of 29 (48.28%) sample mutual fund schemes had outperformed the benchmark return. The results also showed that some of the schemes had underperformed, these schemes were facing the diversification problem. In the study, the Sharpe ratio was positive for all schemes which showed that funds were providing returns greater than risk free rate. Results of Jensen measure revealed that 19 out of 29 (65.52%) schemes were showed positive alpha which indicated superior performance of the schemes.
- The article of **Sathish Kumar et al. (2012) (92)** provides an overview of Indian mutual fund industry. The study analysis the performance of most active type of funds that is ELSS scheme. Using various financial tools the selected fund have been evaluated and ranked.
- The paper by **Sweta Goel, Mukta Mani and Rahul Sharma, (2012) (93)** elaborates the impact of these performance indicators. It has been found that each performance indicator affect the return of the mutual fund independently. This paper also discusses contradictions and the gap present in the literature regarding these performance indicators.

REFERENCES

- 1 Dahlquist, M., S. Engström, P. Söderlind, (2000). Performance and characteristics of Swedish mutual funds. Journal of Financial and quantitative Analysis, 35(03):
-

- 409-423.
- 2 Indro , D . C . , Jiang , C . X . , Hu , M . V . and Lee , W . Y . (2001) Mutual fund performance: Does fund size matter? *Financial Analysts Journal* 55 (3) : 74 – 87.
 - 3 Thomas A Feuerborn (2001). 'Misplaced Marketing', *Journal of consumer Marketing*, Vol 18, No. 1, 7-9.
 - 4 Boyson, N. (2002). "How are Hedge Fund Manager Characteristics Related to Performance, Volatility, and Survival?" (SSRN).
 - 5 Edward S. Daniel E. Page, (2002) "Utility sector mutual funds: sources of performance and dividend policy implications", *Managerial Finance*, 28: 12, pp.14 – 24 .
 - 6 Fortin, R., Michelson , S . and Jordan-Wagner , J . (2002) Does mutual fund manager tenure matter? *Journal of Financial Planning* 12 (7) : 72 – 79 .
 - 7 Syriopoulos (2002), Risk aversion and portfolio allocation to mutual fund classes. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, Vol. 11, 4, Pages 427.
 - 8 Berk, J.B. and Green, R.C. (2004) Mutual fund flows and performance in rational markets, *Journal of Political Economy*, 112, 1269–1295.
 - 9 Mary Jane Lenard, Syed H. Akhter, Pervaiz Alamc, (2003) *Financial Services Review* 12 , 39-59.
 - 10 Qiu, J. (2003) Termination risk, multiple managers and mutual fund tournaments, *European Finance Review*, 7, 161-190.
 - 11 Ronald T. Wilcox. (2003). 'Bargain Hunting or Star Gazing? Investors' Preferences for stock Mutual Funds', *Journal of Business*, Vol. 70, No. 4, 645.
 - 12 Susan Coleman.(2003). ' Risk Tolerance and the Investment Behavior of Black and Hispanic Heads of Household', *Association for Financial Counseling and Planning Education*, 43-51.
 - 13 Berk, J.B. and Green, R.C. (2004) Mutual fund flows and performance in rational markets, *Journal of Political Economy*, 112, 1269–1295.
-

- 14 Dimitrios F. Kenourgios And Ioannis Petropoulos, (2004)The Persistence Of Mutual Funds Performance: Evidence From The Uk Stock Market, *Ekonomia*, Vol. 7, No. 2,
- 15 Paula A Tkac. (2004) .'Mutual Funds: Temporary Problem or Permanent Morass?', *Financial Markets Conference*, 2004 .
- 16 Spiegel, Matthew I., Mamaysky, Harry and Zhang, Hong, (2004) Estimating the Dynamics of Mutual Fund Alphas and Betas .Yale ICF Working Paper No. 03-03; EFA 2003 Annual Conference Paper No. 803; AFA 2004 San Diego Meetings.
- 17 Zhao (2004) ,why are some mutual funds closed to new investors? *Journal of Banking & Finance*, Volume 28, Issue 8, August 2004, Pages 1867-1887.
- 18 Athanasious G. Noulas, John A. Papanastasiou, John Lazaridis (2005). 'Performance of Mutual Funds', *Managerial Finance* Vol 31, No 2, 100-112.
- 19 Cinzia Daraio , Le´opold Simar , A robust nonparametric approach to evaluate and explain the performance of mutual funds, *European Journal of Operational Research* xxx (2005) .
- 20 Gullett , N . S.and Redman , A . L . (2005) Do real estate mutual funds enhance portfolio returns and reduce portfolio risk? *Briefi ngs in Real Estate Finance* 5 : 51 – 66.
- 21 Shefrin, H. and Statman, M. (2005) The disposition to sell winners too early and ride losers too long: Theory and evidence, *Journal of Finance*, 40, 777–790.
- 22 Zakri Y. Bello, (2005) "Socially Responsible Investing and Portfolio Diversification", *The Journal of Financial Research*, Vol. XXVIII, No. 1,2005,41-57.
- 23 Costa, B., K. Jakob, and G. Porter. (2006). "Mutual Fund Performance and Changing Market Trends 1990-2001: Does Manager Experience Matter?"
- 24 Gallagher, D., P. Nadarajay, & M. Pinnuck, (2006), Top management turnover: An examination of portfolio holding and fund performance. *Australian Journal of Management* 31, 265-292.
- 25 Gottesman, A. and M. Morey, (2006). "Manager Education and Mutual Fund
-

- Performance." *Journal of Empirical Finance*, 13: 145-182.
- 26 Jonathan B. Berk and Ian Tonks, (2006) Investing in mutual funds when returns are predictable,"*Journal of Financial Economics*, 81, 339-377.
- 27 Keswani A. and Stolin D., 2006, Mutual Fund Performance Persistence and Competition: A Cross- Sector Analysis, *The Journal of Financial Research*, Vol. 29 No.3, 349-366.
- 28 Bergstresser, Daniel B., Chalmers, John and Tufano, Peter, Assessing the Costs and Benefits of Brokers in the Mutual Fund Industry (October 1, 2007). AFA 2006 Boston Meetings; HBS Finance Working Paper No. 616981. SSRN:<http://ssrn.com/abstract=616981> .
- 29 Elton, Edwin J., Martin J. Gruber, and T. Clifton Green, (2007), The impact of
- 30 Franco, G. and Y. Zhou. (2007). "The Performance of Analysts with a CFA Designation: The Role of Human-Capital and Signaling Theories." (SSRN).
- 31 Jiang, G.G., Yao, T. and Yu, T. (2007). Do mutual funds time the market? Evidence from portfolio holdings. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 86, 724-758.
- 32 Switzer, L. and Y. Huang. (2007). "Management Characteristics and the Performance of Small & Mid Cap Mutual Funds." (SSRN).
- 33 Timotej Jagrica, Boris Podobnikb, Sebastjan Straseka, Vita Jagrica (2007) South-Eastern Europe *Journal of Economics* 234 2 233-24.
- 34 Bliss, R. T., Potter, M. E., & Schwarz, C. (2008). Performance Characteristics of Individually-Managed versus Team-Managed Mutual Funds. *The Journal of Portfolio Management*.
- 35 Dangl, T., Wu, Y. and Zechner, J. (2008) Market discipline and internal governance in the mutual fund industry, *Review of Financial Studies*, 21, 23073.
- 36 Haslem , J . A . , Baker , H . K . and Smith , D . M . (2008) Performance and characteristics of actively managed retail equity mutual funds with diverse
-

- expense ratios . Financial Services Review 17 (1) : 49 – 68.
- 37 Pollet, J.M. and Wilson, M. (2008) How does size affect mutual fund behavior?, Journal of Finance, 63, 2941–2969.
- 38 Ruenzi, Stefan, and Alexander Kempf, 2008, Tournaments in Mutual Fund Families, Review of Financial Studies 21, 1013{1036.
- 39 Wu, Cheng-Ru, Hsin-Yuan Chang and Li-Syuan Wu,(2008), “A Framework of Assessable Mutual Fund Performance,” Journal of Modelling in Management, Vol. 3, No. 2, pages 125-139.
- 40 Comer, George, Norris Larrymore and Javier Rodriguez, (2009) “Measuring the Value of Active Fund Management: The Case of Hybrid Mutual Funds,” Managerial Finance, Vol. 35, No. 1,, pages 63-77.
- 41 Ivković & weisbenner (2009) studied the research paper on Individual investor mutual fund flows Journal of Financial Economics, Volume 92, Issue 2, May 2009, pp. 223.
- 42 James L. Kuhle and Rafiqul Bhuyan, (2009), Sub-Par Performance In A Sub-Prime World? A Recent Comparative Performance Analysis Of Real Estate Mutual Funds Vs. Common Stock Mutual Funds, Journal of Business & Economics Research – Vol.7, No.8.
- 43 Kempf, A., Ruenzi, S. and Thiele, T. (2009) Employment risk, compensation incentives, and managerial risk taking: Evidence from the mutual fund industry, Journal of Financial Economics, 92, 92-108.
- 44 Nur Atiqah Abdullah and Nur Adiana Hiau Abdullah, (2009), The Performance Of Malaysian Unit Trusts Investing In Domestic Versus International Markets, Asian Academy Of Management Journal Of Accounting And Finance, AAMJAF, Vol. 5, No. 2, 77–100.
- 45 Cummings, Benjamin F., The Effect of Mutual Fund Fees on Performance: A Review of the Literature for Practitioners (February 24, 2010). SSRN:
-

<http://ssrn.com/abstract=1967307>.

- 46 Hereil, Pierre, Mitaine, Philippe, Moussavi, Nicolas and Roncalli, Thierry Mutual Fund Ratings and Performance Persistence (, 2010). SSRN: <http://ssrn.com/abstract>.
- 47 Cici, G., Cprgel, J. and Gibson, S. (2011). Can fund managers select outperforming REITs? Examining fund holding and trades. *Real Estate Economics*, 39 (30), 455-486.
- 48 Hui-chuan Chen, (2011), Analysis of Consumer Reports ' recommended mutual funds compared to actual performance *Journal of Financial Services Marketing* 16, 42 – 49.
- 49 Irfan Ullah Shah, Junaid Iqbal and Muhammad Faizan Malik, (2012), Comparative Valuation between Islamic and Conventional Mutual Fund, *International Research Journal of Finance and Economics*, ISSN 1450-2887 : 96.
- 50 Jin-Li Hu, Hsueh-E. Yu and Yi-Ting Wang, (2012) Manager Attributes and Fund Performance: Evidence from Taiwan, *Journal of Applied Finance & Banking*, vol.2, no.4, 85-101.
- 51 Junare S. O. and Frena Patel, (2012), Analysis Of Perceptions Of Investors Towards Mutual Funds: An Empirical Investigation, *International Journal Of Research In Commerce & Management*, Volume No. 3 , Issue No. 5 .
- 52 Majid Abbasi and Majid Dadashinasab, (2012) Mutual Fund Managers'
- 53 Nasir Razzâq, (2012) "Conventional Mutual Funds And Their Performance In Pakistan", *Asian Journal of Business and Management Sciences* ISSN: 2047-2528 Vol. 1 No. 12 [54-69].
- 54 Irissappane, Aravazhi (2000). "Paradigm Shifts In The Performance Of Indian Mutual Funds: An Analysis With Reference To Close-Ended Funds Of Selected Institutions", UTI Institute of Capital Markets, Mumbai.
-

- 55 Jain, Prem C., (2000) Truth in Mutual Fund Advertising: Evidence on Future Performance and Fund Flows, *Journal of Finance* 55, 937-958.
- 56 Roshni Jayam, "Debt Be Not Proud, Equity's Back", (2002)*Business Today*, pp.42-45.
- 57 Rajeeva Sinha and Vijay Jog, (2005),Returns To Mutual Fund Investors A Study Of Canadian Mutual Fund, *ASAC* 2005 May 28-31,
- 58 Anand, S. and Murugaiah, V. (2006). Analysis of Components of Investment
- 59 Nalini Prava Tripathy, (2006) Market Timing Abilities and Mutual Fund Performance- An Empirical Investigation into Equity Linked Saving Schemes, *Vilakshan, XIMB Journal of Management*, pp. 127-138
- 60 Rao, D. N., (2006)Investment Styles and Performance of Equity Mutual Funds in India , Available at SSRN: <http://ssrn.com/abstract>
- 61 Rao , S . P . U . and Schaub , M . (2006) Impact of 12b-I fees on expense ratios of large-cap growth, mid-cap growth, small-cap growth, and income objective mutual funds . *Journal of Business and Society* 19 (1/2) : 250 – 260 .
- 62 Hanumantha Rao P and Vijay KR. Mishra (2007), "Mutual Fund: A Resource Mobiliser in Financial Market", *Vidyasagar University Journal of Commerce*, Vol.1
- 63 Sanjay Kant Khare 2007, "Mutual Funds: A Refuge for Small Investors", *Southern Economist*, (January 15, 2007), pp.21-24.
- 64 Guha, S. (2008). Performance of Indian Equity Mutual Funds vis-a-vis their Style Benchmarks. *The ICAFI Journal of Applied Finance*, 14, 1: 49-81.
- 65 Agrawa, D. (2009). A Comparative Study of Equity Based Mutual Fund of Reliance and HDFC. *ASAC* 2005 September, 45-52,
- 66 Kavitha Chavali , Shefali Jain.(2009). 'Investment Performance of Equity-Linked Saving Schemes- An Empirical Study', *India Journal of Finance*, 15-22.
- 67 Ravi Kiran. (2009) . 'An analysis of investor's risk Perception towards Mutual Funds
-

- Services', International Journal of business and Management, Vol 4, No. 5, 106-120.
- 68 Sathya Swaroop Debasish, (2009).Investigating Performance of Equity-based Mutual Fund Schemes in Indian Scenario, Kca Journal Of Business Management. Vol. 2, Issue 2
- 69 Prabakaran, G and Jayabal, G (2010). Performance Evaluation of Mutual Fund Schemes in India: An Empirical Study. Finance India, 24 (4), 1347-1363
- 70 Ranganathan, Kavitha, (2010), A Study of Fund Selection Behaviour of Individual Investors Towards Mutual Funds - with Reference to Mumbai City (2006). Indian Institute of Capital Markets 9th Capital Markets Conference
- 71 Sondhi, H.J and Jain, P.K (2010). Market Risk and Investment Performance of Equity Mutual Funds in India: Some Empirical Evidence. Finance India, XXIV (2), 443-464.
- 72 Devasenathipathi, T. (2011), A comparative analysis of market returns and fund flows with reference to mutual Funds, international journal of research in commerce, it & management, Volume No. 1, Issue No. 4, pp 62-65
- 73 Garg, Sanjay (2011). A Study on Performance Evaluation of Selected Indian Mutual
- 74 Manisha Goel and Shelly Singhal, (2011)To Evaluate Whether One Time Investment Or Systematic Investment Plan Would Give Higher Returns And To Find Out The Top Five Schemes On The Basis Of Return– A Case Study Of HDFC Bank, IJRFM Vol. 1,
- 75 Santhi N. S and K. Balanaga Gurunathan (2011), An Analysis of Investors' Attitude towards Tax Saving Mutual Funds in India, European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences, ISSN: 1450-2275, Issue 41 (2011) ©
- 76 Selvam, Murugesan and Palanisamy, Bhuvanewari, (2011). Analysis of Risk and Return Relationship of Indian Equity (Dividend) Mutual Fund Schemes Available at SSRN: <http://ssrn.com/abstract>
-

- 77 Simran Saini; Bimal Anjum; Ramandeep Saini; (2011) Investors' Awareness And Perception About Mutual Funds , ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary
- 78 Sumninder Kaur Bawa and Smiti Brar (2011) Performance Evaluation Of Income
- 79 Surinder Kr. Miglani, (2011)Market Timing Ability of Indian Mutual Funds, VSRD
- 80 Avani Shah and Narayan Baser (2012), Mutual Fund: Behavioral Finance's Perspective, IRJC, Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing & Management Review Vol.1 No. 2, October 2012, ISSN 2319-2836
- 81 Bimal Anjum' Sukhwinder Kaur Dhanda , G.S.Batra, , (2012), Performance Evaluation Of Selected Open Ended Mutual Funds In India, International Journal Of Marketing, Financial Services & Management Research Vol.1 No. 1, ISSN 2277 3622
- 82 Bijan Roy and Kaushik Bhattacharjee, (2012), International Journal of Information Technology and Business Management, Vol.5 No. 1
- 83 Ghose, Soheli. (2012), Sector holdings in mutual fund performance: an analysis, IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSRJBM) ISSN : 2278-487X Vo.1, PP 29-39
- 84 Gomathy Thyagarajan (2012), Performance Evaluation of Indian Mutual Fund Industry from 2002-2007 with Special Reference to Franklin Templeton, HDFC and ICICI Prudential Mutual Funds, Ninth AIMS International Conference on Management January 1-4, 2012
- 85 Kalpesh P Prajapati, and Mahesh K Patel, (2012) Comparative Study On Performance Evaluation Of Mutual Fund Schemes Of Indian Companies , International Refereed Research Journal | www.researchersworld.com | Vol-III, Issue3(3), [47]
- 86 Nimalathasan B; Kumar Gandhi R. (2012), Mutual Fund Financial Performance Analysis- A Comparative Study On Equity Diversified Schemes And Equity Mid-Cap Schemes, EXCEL International Journal of Multidisciplinary Management Studies
-

Vol.2

- 87 Ravi Vyas, Mutual Fund Investor's Behaviour And Perception In Indore City,(2012) International Refereed Research Journal www.researchersworld.com Vol.. III, Issue.3(1),July [67]
- 88 Sahit Chowdary Garapati, (2012) (13) Performance Evaluation Based Rating of Indian Equity Mutual Funds - A New Approach , International Research Journal of Finance and Economics, ISSN 1450-2887 Issue 97
- 89 Sarita Bahl; Meenakshi Rani, 2012, A Comparative Analysis Of Mutual Fund Schemes In India, International Journal of Marketing, Financial Services & Management Research Vol.1 Issue 7,
- 90 Sathish Kumar B, Elgin A and V. R. Nedunchezian, (2012) Financial Performance of Selected Indian Mutual Funds Schemes, European Journal of Social Sciences ISSN 1450-2267 Vol.29 No.3, pp. 450-457
- 91 Sweta Goel, Mukta Mani and Rahul Sharma, (2012) A Review Of Performance Indicators Of Mutual Funds, International Refereed Research Journal,